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3 **Electrolyzed Acid Water: a clean technology active on fungal vascular pathogens in**
4 **grapevine nurseries**

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11

12 **Abstract**

13 *Phaeomoniella chlamydospora* (Pch) and *Phaeoacremonium minimum* (Pmi) are among the
14 main grapevine trunk disease pathogens in the nursery. These pathogens can cause latent
15 infections of the propagation material often appearing as dark wood streaking, and are
16 associated with decline occurrence in young vineyards. The infection may occur during the
17 grafting process, particularly during hydration. Promising preliminary results were obtained
18 in the nursery using electrolyzed acid water (EAW) for the hydration of cuttings; EAW is
19 characterized by low values of pH (2.5), high oxidation reduction potential (ORP>1000) and
20 a certain amount of free chlorine. No differences in absorption kinetics were recorded
21 between EAW and tap water, nor among 1103P, K5BB and SO4 rootstocks. In all
22 combinations no significant additional absorption was observed after 7 hours of immersion.

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23 In order to assess the characteristics of EAW after the contact with the inner plant tissues
24 ORP and pH were measured from the liquid extracted from rootstocks after immersion in
25 EAW. The values of the liquid, named “weakened” EAW (wEAW) (625-650 mV ORP and
26 3.1-3.3 pH), were significantly different from the values of both EAW and the liquid extracted
27 after immersion in tap water. When the propagation material had been hydrated for 7 hr in
28 EAW no significant effect on vegetating growth performance and percentage of certifiable
29 plants was ever observed for SO4 or 1103P, whereas a reduction in plant vegetative growth
30 was observed in K5BB hydrated vines at 12hr hydration. EAW and wEAW gave no
31 significant reduction of *in vitro* mycelial growth, whereas a consistent decrease in conidial
32 germination was observed in Pch and Pmi. The three-year experiments carried out in the
33 nursery on cuttings inoculated with Pch and hydrated in EAW showed a remarkable
34 reduction of the infection level in the treated plants.

35

36 *Keyword:*

37 Environmentally friendly control strategy

38 Electrolized Acid Water

39 Grapevine nursery process

40 *Phaeomoniella chlamydospora*

41 *Phaeoacremonium minimum*

42

431. Introduction

44 The tracheomycotic fungi *Phaeomoniella chlamydospora* (Pch) and *Phaeoacremonium*
45 species, of which *P. minimum* (syn. *P. aleophilum*) is the most common (Pmi) are pathogens
46 associated with most diseases within the Esca complex (Surico et al, 2008). Esca complex
47 is undoubtedly the most important grapevine trunk disease in Europe and affects plants

48 throughout their entire lifetime, causing slow decline, yield losses and death of the vine
49 (Mugnai et al., 1999; Bertsch et al., 2013).

50 In the nursery, dark wood streaking caused by Pch and Pmi is found in the rootstocks of
51 apparently healthy grafted cuttings (Bertelli et al., 1998; Halleen et al., 2003; Edwards and
52 Pascoe, 2004). The infection may occur during the nursery production process particularly
53 at cane harvesting from mother plants, hydration, grafting and waxing, callusing and also in
54 the nursery field (Gramaje and Armengol, 2011). In particular, Pch and, less frequently, Pmi
55 or other *Phaeoacremonium* species, were detectable in hydration (tanks and water), which
56 appears to be a major source of infection in the nursery process (Whiteman et al., 2004;
57 Mostert et al., 2006; Retief et al., 2006; Edwards et al., 2007; Aroca et al., 2010; Gramaje
58 and Armengol, 2011).

59 Pch and Pmi are therefore known as agents of latent infections of the propagation material
60 and can often be associated with decline in young vineyards. Great efforts are underway to
61 develop an effective control of fungal trunk pathogens in the nursery. Fungicides, such as
62 thiophanate methyl, captan, mancozeb, thiram and 8-hydroxyquinoline sulfate (the most
63 commonly used compound), are also used to suppress *Botrytis cinerea* in the nursery and
64 some have been tested for their efficacy on GTDs, but with no great success. More
65 promising results on the reduction of incidence or severity of Pch and Pmi are being obtained
66 with biological control agents (mostly *Trichoderma* spp. based formulations) applied at
67 hydration stage of the cuttings before or at the grafting process (Di Marco et al., 2004; Fourie
68 et al., 2001; Pertot et al., 2016).

69 Electrolyzed acid water (EAW) is produced by electrolysis of pure water containing sodium
70 or potassium chloride. Electrolysis is done in a special chamber that allows the anodic and
71 cathodic solutions to be separated. EAW is produced at the anode while alkaline water is
72 produced at the cathode (Ongeng et al., 2006; Artés et al., 2009). EAW is characterized by

73 low pH, ranging from 2.3 to 2.7, a high oxidation reduction potential (ORP>1000) and an
74 increased concentration of free chlorine (Koseki *et al.*, 2001; Li *et al.*, 2014).

75 The electrolyzed water (acid and not) is used for the treatment of surgical instruments, and
76 has proved to be effective as a disinfectant both for animal products and for preservation
77 or cold sterilization of food products (Huang *et al.*, 2008). The antimicrobial activity of EAW
78 is associated with the combination of free chlorine, low pH and high ORP, (Kiura *et al.*,
79 2002; Abbasi and Lazarovitis, 2006; Huang *et al.*, 2008).

80 EAW has strong bactericidal activity (Artés *et al.*, 2009; Huang *et al.*, 2008; Wang *et al.*,
81 2014), but it is also effective against spore germination of several plant pathogenic fungi
82 such as *Botrytis* spp., *Botryosphaeria dothidea* and *B. berengeriana* (Al-Haq *et al.*, 2002),
83 *Fusarium* spp., *Cladosporium* spp., *Helminthosporium* spp., *Colletotrichum* spp. *Epicoccum*
84 *nigrum*, *Monilinia fructicola*, *Diaporthe longicolla* (as *Phomopsis longicolla*; Buck, Iersel,
85 Oetting & Hung, 2002), *Aspergillus flavus* (Xiong *et al.*, 2014), *Penicillium expansum* (Okull
86 and Laborde, 2004), and *Tilletia indica* (Bonde *et al.*, 1999). Moreover, spray treatments of
87 electrolyzed acid water gave significant control of powdery mildew in gerbera daisy and
88 greenhouse rose varieties (Martinez-Espinoza *et al.*, 2003).

89 Preliminary studies carried out in the nursery have shown the potential of EAW to reduce
90 infections by Pch and Pmi in rootstock cuttings during hydration before the grafting process.
91 Laboratory assays also demonstrated that EAW reduced Pch and Pmi conidial germination
92 at 4 and 11°C (Di Marco and Osti, 2009).

93 The objective of this study was to determine: (i) the activity of EAW on mycelial growth and
94 conidial germination of Pch and Pmi; (ii) the rate of absorption of EAW by rootstocks during
95 the hydration process; (iii) the pH and ORP of the liquid extracted from rootstocks after
96 immersion in EAW; (iv) the effects of EAW on vegetative growth of grafted cuttings in the
97 nursery field and on certifiable plants; (v) the activity of EAW on grafted vines previously
98 inoculated with Pch and grown in the nursery field.

1002. **Materials and methods**

101

102 *2.1. Fungal cultures*

103

104 Cultures of *Phaeoconiella chlamydospora* (Pch) (CBS 229.95) and *Phaeoacremonium*
105 *minimum* (Pmi) (CBS 631.94) were grown on Potato Dextrose Agar or Malt Agar (PDA or
106 MA; Becton, Dickinson & Co, Sparks, MD, USA) at 25°C in a growth chamber with a 16:8 h
107 photoperiod (light/dark). Three-week-old cultures were used for mycelial growth and conidial
108 germination assays.

109

110 *2.2. Electrolyzed acid water (EAW)*

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112 EAW was produced from a unit including a reverse osmosis water treatment system and an
113 Electrolyzed Water generator (prototype EAW AG25; CBC Europe Srl, Nova Milanese, Italy)
114 by electrolysis of a saturated potassium chloride solution (Carlo Erba Reagents, Milan, Italy).
115 Current and voltage applied across the electrodes were fixed to obtain acid and alkaline
116 water within an expected range of pH and oxidation-reduction potential (ORP), and free
117 residual chlorine for the acidic fraction. Measurements of pH, ORP and free chlorine of
118 freshly prepared water were made with a digital model HI 8417 microprocessor-controlled
119 pH/mV meter (Hanna Instruments, Milan, Italy) equipped with electrodes HI1131B (Hanna
120 Instruments) for pH, and Pt4805-DPA-SC-S8/120 (Mettler-Toledo, Novate Milanese, Milan,
121 Italy) for ORP. An electrode 17B combined with an automatic titrator (Titroline 96, Schott,
122 Germany), was used to determine the concentration of free active chlorine. Experiments
123 were conducted with freshly prepared electrolyzed water with the following values: pH 2.5–
124 2.6; ORP 1120–1129 mV, and free chlorine 40–42 ppm. A further type of electrolyzed acid

125 water named “weakened EAW” (wEAW), with pH 3.1–3.3; ORP 625–650 mV values, was
126 prepared following the data obtained in the experiment of liquid extraction from rootstocks
127 immersed in EAW, as described below.

128

129 *2.3. Mycelial growth assay*

130

131 Discs (5 mm diam.) of agar colonized by mycelium were cut from the edge of Pch and Pmi
132 colonies and placed in the centre of a Petri dish containing PDA. Soon after inoculation of
133 the medium and every 2 days until the end of the experiment, EAW, wEAW or sterile tap-
134 water (control), were gently applied to the mycelium to ensure a complete covering of the
135 whole colony, taking care to avoid dispersal of conidia onto the agar. Petri dishes were
136 incubated in a growth chamber at the conditions described for fungal culture preparation.
137 There were five replicates per treatment (each replicate consisting of one Petri dish). Radial
138 growth of each colony was periodically measured (two diameters per Petri dish) over a
139 period of 25 days. Data were expressed as mean colony diameters (mm).

140

141 *2.4. Influence of time of exposure to EAW or wEAW on conidial germination*

142

143 Conidia were harvested by flooding Pch and Pmi cultures with sterile water containing 0.1%
144 Tween 20 (Sigma Aldrich co., St Louis, MO, USA). The resulting suspension was filtered
145 through sterile cheesecloth. The conidial suspension of each fungus was then resuspended
146 in sterile water, the concentration of conidia determined with a Bürker cell-counting chamber
147 (Glaswarenfabrik Karl Hecht GmbH & Co KG, Sondheim v. d. Rhön, Germany) under light
148 microscopy and adjusted to 1×10^6 conidia ml⁻¹.

149 Fifty microliters of conidial suspensions were mixed with 950 µl of EAW or wEAW for 0, 30,
150 60 or 120 s (Buck *et al.*, 2002). Exposure was stopped by adding 9 ml of neutralizing buffer

151 (Difco Laboratories, Detroit, MI, USA) at pH 7.2. For each treatment, 200 µl of spore
152 suspension was mixed with 50 µl of yeast nitrogen base with 2% glucose (Becton, Dickinson
153 & Co, Sparks MD), and incubated in 96-well microtiter plates in the dark, at 25° C for 48 h.
154 After incubation, 20 µl of conidial suspension was transferred to a glass slide, covered with
155 a cover slip, and observed by light microscopy. A conidium was considered as germinated
156 if the length of a primary germ tube was equal to at least the length of a conidium (Jaspers,
157 2001). One hundred conidia per treatment were assessed for germination in three replicates.
158 Results were expressed as percentage of conidia germinated. All experiments were
159 repeated two times with comparable results.

160

161 *2.5. Rootstock water absorption*

162

163 Dormant rootstocks from a commercial nursery, 30–35 cm long *V. berlandieri* x *V. riparia*
164 K5BB and SO4, and *V. berlandieri* x *V. rupestris* 1103P were individually labelled, weighed
165 on an analytical balance (Exacta, Alessandrini, Modena, Italy) and completely immersed in
166 a plastic tray containing 10 L of EAW or tap-water for the control. For each rootstock and
167 type of water 12 cuttings each representing one replicate were used. Water absorption was
168 recorded as cutting weight increase at 1, 3, 5, 7, 12, and 24 hours after rootstock immersion.
169 For each time of assessment each cutting was removed from the water, laid on absorbent
170 paper for 1 min, wiped lightly with a cotton cloth, and weighed accurately. Moreover, at each
171 time of assessment pH and ORP were checked by directly immersing the electrodes in EAW
172 at a distance of about 5 cm from the cuttings (3 measurements per time of assessment).
173 Results are expressed as mean weight increase of rootstocks (g) at each time of immersion.
174 All experiments were repeated two times with comparable results.

175

176 *2.6. Analysis of liquid extracted from rootstocks immersed in water and EAW*

177

178 The experiment was carried out to verify the pH and ORP of the liquid extracted from
179 rootstocks after immersion in EAW or tap water. Preliminary trials carried out on the three
180 different rootstock cultivars showed that K5BB was not suitable for the experiment because
181 of the limited amount of liquid extracted with the adopted method. One hundred and fifty
182 rootstocks cv 1103P and cv SO4 were completely immersed in three plastic boxes (50
183 rootstocks per box) each containing 30 L of EAW and representing 2 times of assessment.
184 For each cultivar, a further 150 rootstocks were immersed in tap water as control. At 7 or 12
185 hours after immersion, rootstocks were removed and rapidly wiped with a cotton cloth. A
186 soft transparent rubber tube (13 cm length, 0.9 cm internal diameter) was fixed at the bottom
187 end of each rootstock. The tube was connected to an air compressor (Mirage Mustang
188 Breton, Fully Corsair 850/25, Cascina Vica, Turin, Italy). Air at 4 bar pressure was applied
189 through the tube to the plant and after 15–20 s, about 40–50 µl of liquid per rootstock were
190 collected in a test tube. A total amount of 2 ml of water per time of immersion was collected
191 from each type of rootstock and immediately analysed for pH and ORP. The experiment was
192 repeated the following year with both cultivars as described above. The mean of the results
193 obtained in the two annual experiments were expressed for pH and ORP at each time of
194 immersion.

195

196 *2.7. EAW treatment influence on quality of grafted plants*

197

198 Trials were carried out in a commercial nursery. Groups of 900 cuttings (3 buds, 40 cm
199 length) 1103P, SO4 or K5BB were subjected to 7 and 12 hours of hydration in tanks
200 containing EAW (tap water for the control). Trebbiano Romagnolo shoots were omega-
201 grafted onto each treated rootstock. Plants were dipped in paraffin wax and each group was
202 stacked with sawdust in separate callusing boxes and stored at 10–20°C for 3 weeks. Vines

203 were planted in the nursery field in alternate rows each consisting of 300 plants of the same
204 rootstock (1103P, SO4, or K5BB). Three rows for each rootstock were set up. Vines were
205 periodically investigated for vegetative growth. Twenty-six weeks after planting, vines were
206 uprooted following the commercial nursery procedures and “certifiable plants” were
207 arbitrarily selected by nurserymen according to EU directive 2005/43. For each rootstock-
208 scion combination, three replicates each consisting of 200 vines collected from one row,
209 were examined. The percentage of vegetating and certifiable plants for each treatment was
210 calculated. A second trial was repeated the following year. Data are expressed as the
211 percentage of vegetating and certifiable plants.

212

213 *2.8 Artificial inoculation of rootstocks with Pch*

214

215 The activity of EAW in the nursery field was assessed in three different experiments carried
216 out in a preliminary experiment (2013) and in 2014 and 2015. For each year and type of
217 experiment, at the beginning of March, 160 cuttings of each rootstock (SO4, K5BB, 1103P),
218 were put in PVC containers and immediately inoculated by soaking for 2 hours the basal-
219 end (2 cm from the basal cut) in a conidial suspension of Pch (CBS 229.95). Inoculum
220 concentration was 5×10^6 conidia ml^{-1} in 2013, and 1×10^5 conidia ml^{-1} in the 2014 and 2015
221 experiments. The conidial suspension was gently stirred with a plastic rod to avoid the
222 conidia sinking to the bottom of the container. Eighty cuttings that were immersed in water
223 were used as control. All cuttings were then placed in cold storage at 10°C (approx.) for 45
224 days.

225

226 *2.9. Activity of EAW in the nursery on rootstocks inoculated with Pch*

227

228 After 45 days of cold storage following artificial inoculation, 80 cuttings were randomly
229 selected from each rootstock and hydrated in 10 litres of EAW or in 10 litres of tap water for
230 the inoculated control for 7 hours. Trebbiano Romagnolo shoots were omega-grafted onto
231 plants of each rootstock. Grafted plants were callused in sawdust for 3 weeks. At the end of
232 the callusing period, grafted plants were left for 1 more week in a greenhouse at about 15°
233 C with the basal end dipped in water for acclimation, and then planted in the nursery field.
234 Before planting, thirty plants for each treatment were sampled to evaluate the viability of Pch
235 by plating 10 wood fragments each taken at 1 cm from the basal wound.

236 In the preliminary experiment (2013), plants were collected from the nursery field at about
237 1, 3 and 5 months (end of growing season) after planting. In 2014 and 2015, plants non-
238 inoculated and treated with tap water were also considered. Plants were collected at the end
239 of the growing season only. Bark was removed and the external surface of the vine was
240 quickly flamed. Transversal sections 1.5 mm thick were made at 5 and 15 cm (experiment
241 2013) or at 2, 5, 10, 15 and 20 cm (experiment 2014 and 2015) from the bottom end of the
242 plant. For each woody section, 5–6 fragments were placed on PDA to assess the
243 development of Pch colonies in the treated and untreated vines. Twenty plants for each
244 treatment and each time of investigation were assessed. For each year and rootstock-scion
245 combination, data were expressed as the percentage of fragments fertile for Pch at each
246 time of assessment and distance from the bottom end of the plant.

247

248 *2.10. Statistical analysis.*

249

250 All assessment data were analysed by analysis of variance (ANOVA) at $P = 0.05$. Tukey's
251 test with a confidence level of 0.95 were performed in the following experiments to assess
252 differences between: conidial germination with (i) time of exposure to EAW or wEAW; (ii)
253 water absorption by cuttings relative to time of immersion in EAW; (iii) percentage of

254 certifiable plants for each rootstock-scion combination with the time of immersion in EAW;(iv)
255 percentage of fertile fragments for Pch with the distance from the site of inoculation
256 (experiment 2014 and 2015). All statistical analyses were performed using SAS system
257 software, Version 9.1 (SAS Institute, Cary, NC, USA).

258

259

2603. Results

261

262 3.1. Mycelial growth assay

263

264 For each time of assessment and pathogen, no significant ($P=0.05$) differences between
265 EAW, wEAW and sterile tap-water control could be detected in the colony growth (Fig. 1).

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268

269 **Fig. 1.** Mycelial growth on PDA of colonies of *Pch* (A) and *Pmi* (B) treated with tap water (control),
 270 weakened Electrolyzed Acidic Water (wEAW) or Electrolyzed Acidic Water (EAW). Values are the
 271 mean of five replicates, each represented by the mean of two diameters per colony.

272

273 3.2. *Conidial germination assay*

274 Conidial germination rates in the untreated control (0 s of exposure to EAW) ranged from 82
 275 to 88% for *Pch*, and from 82 to 89% for *Pmi* (Fig. 2). Thirty seconds of exposure to EAW
 276 were sufficient to significantly ($P < 0.05$) reduce the percentage of conidial germination for
 277 both pathogens. The greatest reduction of germination of *Pch* was achieved at 120 s of
 278 exposure when only 10% of the conidia germinated compared to 88% in the control (Fig.
 279 2A). Increasing the exposure time did not cause any further increase of EAW activity towards
 280 conidial germination of *Pmi* (Fig. 2B). For both pathogens, the activity of wEAW on conidial
 281 germination was statistically ($P < 0.05$) significant at 60 s of exposure, reaching the maximum
 282 of 58% and 32% of reduction at 120 s (Fig. 2).

283

284

285 **Fig. 2.** Germination of conidia of *Pch* (A) and *Pmi* (B) treated with wEAW, or EAW (control = 0
 286 seconds of exposure). Values are the mean of three replicates, each represented by 100 conidia.
 287 Different capital and lower letters for wEAW and EAW respectively, indicate significant difference at
 288 P level of 0.05 for Tukey's HDS test.

289

290 3.3 Rootstocks water absorption

291 For each rootstock and time of assessment, no significant differences could be detected
292 between EAW and tap-water ($P=0.05$). The maximum EAW absorption assessed after 24
293 hours of hydration was 2.61, 2.16 and 1.54 g for 1103P, SO4 and K5BB rootstocks
294 respectively. The three rootstocks showed the same absorption kinetics; at 7 hours of
295 immersion the amount of water absorbed was not significantly different ($P=0.05$) from that
296 observed at 24 hours (Fig. 3). At each time of assessment, the pH and ORP of EAW
297 recorded in the plastic trays did not change compared to the values registered at the
298 beginning of the experiment.

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302

303 **Fig. 3.** Water absorption of 1103P (A), SO4 (B) and K5BB (C) cuttings at different time of the
 304 hydration in EAW or tap water (control). Values represent the mean of 12 replicates, each
 305 represented by 1 cutting. For each type of water, the absorption at different time is compared with

306 Tukey's HDS test and statistical analysis is presented according to the color of the curve. For each
307 treatment, different letters indicate significant differences at P level 0.05.

308

309 3.4 Analysis of liquid extracted from rootstocks immersed in water and EAW

310 Results are summarized in Figure 4. For both 1103P and SO4 rootstocks the values of ORP
311 and pH of the liquid extracted after 7 and 12 hours of immersion in EAW, differed significantly
312 ($P < 0.05$) from the liquid extracted from rootstocks immersed in tap water. The values of
313 ORP (625–650 mV) and pH (3.1–3.3) of the liquid extracted from rootstocks immersed in
314 EAW did not vary with the time of immersion or the type of rootstock, but were always lower
315 than those in the original EAW water, so the extracted liquid was referred to as “weakened
316 EAW” (wEAW).

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319

320 **Fig. 4.** Values of pH (A) and ORP (B) of the liquid extracted at different times of hydration of 1103P
 321 and SO4 rootstocks in EAW or tap water (control). Values represent the mean of two replicates,
 322 each represented by one annual experiment. For each rootstock at each time of exposure, the
 323 significance between tap water and EAW is calculated by ANOVA $P < 0.05$ and indicated with an
 324 asterisk over the bars.

325

326 3.5 Vegetating and certifiable grafted plants

327 No significant ($P=0.05$) effect on vegetating and certifiable plants was observed for SO4 or
 328 1103P rootstocks (Table 1). The hydration of K5BB cuttings with EAW had different effects
 329 on plant vegetation depending on the time of immersion (Table 1). In both years of
 330 investigation, 12 hours of immersion in EAW gave significantly ($P<0.05$) lower percentage
 331 of vegetating and certifiable cuttings compared to 7 hours of immersion in EAW, or 7 and 12
 332 hours in tap water.

333

334 **Table 1**

335 Percentage of vegetating and certifiable cuttings treated with EAW or tap water (control) during the hydration. Data were assessed at the end of the
 336 growth period in the nursery soil. For each treatment, values are the mean of three replicates each represented by 200 vines. For each year and
 337 time of immersion, EAW and tap water (control) are compared with Tukey's HDS test. Values followed by different letter indicate significant difference
 338 at P level of 0.05.

Time of Immersion (h) / treatment	1103P				SO4				K5BB			
	2013		2014		2013		2014		2013		2014	
	V ¹	C ²	V	C	V	C	V	C	V	C	V	C
7 / Tap water	85a ³	71a	89a	82a	76a	67a	90a	80a	67a ³	54a	94a	84a
7 / EAW	86a	72a	95a	90a	71a	67a	90a	83a	62a	50a	84a	76a
12 / Tap water	87a	70a	88a	79a	78a	70a	89a	85a	72a	56a	88a	77a
12 / EAW	62a	58a	84a	81a	69a	62a	81a	76a	43b	38b	59b	58b

339 ¹ Percentage of vegetating plants.

340 ² Percentage of certifiable plants according to EU directive 2005/43.

341 ³ Values in column followed by the same letter do not differ significantly according to Duncan's Multiple Range test (P=0.05).

342 3.6. Activity of EAW in the nursery on rootstock cuttings inoculated with *Pch*

343 Inoculations were all successful (at least one fragment/plant yielded *Pch*). In the 2013
344 preliminary experiment (Fig. 5) the percentage of fragments colonised by *Pch* in the
345 untreated control was high but localized near the bottom end of the cutting (5 cm) that had
346 been immersed in the spore suspension. No fertile fragments were recorded at 15 cm, both
347 in the treated and in the untreated cuttings and, consequently, no difference between control
348 and EAW-treated plants could be detected at 15 cm. However, at the 5 cm level, hydration
349 in EAW reduced the percentage of infected fragments in all rootstock-scion combinations.
350 For each time of assessment, the level of reduction of colonization in EAW treated plants
351 compared with the controls decreased during the growing season but re-isolation success
352 was always significantly ($P<0.05$) lower in the EAW treatments, except for the SO4 grafted
353 plants assessed at the end of the growing season (Fig. 5).

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358 **Fig. 5.** Re-isolations of *Pch* carried out during the nursery field period (2013 preliminary experiment)
 359 on 1103P (A), SO4 (B), or K5BB (C) rootstocks artificially inoculated at the basal end with *Pch* treated
 360 in hydration with tap water or EAW. Rootstocks were then grafted with cv. Trebbiano Romagnolo.
 361 Re-isolations were carried out at 5 cm from the inoculation site. Values are the mean of 20 replicates,

362 each represented by 1 plant. For each date of assessment, the significance between tap water and
363 EAW is calculated by ANOVA $P < 0.05$ and indicated with an asterisk over the bars.

364 In the 2014 and 2015 experiments, despite the lower inoculum concentration, fragments
365 infected by Pch were found up to 15–20 cm from the bottom end of the cuttings (Fig. 6, 7).

366 Pch reisolation at 5 cm was lower, compared to 2013.

367 In the 2014 and 2015 experiments EAW treatment significantly ($P < 0.05$) reduced the
368 percentage of colonised fragments compared with Pch inoculated plants at 5 to 20 cm from
369 the site of inoculation.

370 In 2014 and 2015 also non inoculated and non treated control vines (naturally infected) were
371 analysed. Except for the isolations carried out at the site of inoculation (2 cm from the bottom
372 end) and at 5 cm for SO4 only, the percentage of fertile fragments from naturally infected
373 plants did not differ significantly ($P = 0.05$) from the fertile fragments obtained from the EAW
374 treated vines (Fig. 6, 7).

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379 **Fig. 6.** Re-isolations of *Pch* carried out at the end of the nursery field period (2014 experiment) on
 380 1103P (A), SO4 (B), or K5BB (C) rootstocks non-inoculated and treated in tap water (i), artificially
 381 inoculated at the basal end with *Pch* treated in hydration with tap water (ii) or EAW (iii). Rootstocks
 382 were then grafted with cv. Trebbiano Romagnolo. Re-isolation of *Pch* was carried out at the end of

383 the nursery field period, at different distance from the site of inoculation. Values are the mean of 20
384 replicates, each represented by 1 plant. For each time of assessment, the significance between
385 treatments was calculated according to Tukey's HSD test. Different letters indicate significant
386 differences at *P* level 0.05.

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389

390 **Fig. 7.** Re-isolations of *Pch* carried out at the end of the nursery field period (2015 experiment) on
 391 1103P (A), SO4 (B), or K5BB (C) rootstocks non-inoculated and treated in tap water (i), artificially
 392 inoculated at the basal end with *Pch* treated in hydration with tap water (ii) or EAW (iii). Rootstocks

393 were then grafted with cv. Trebbiano Romagnolo. Re-isolation of Pch was carried out at the end of
394 the nursery field period, at different distance from the site of inoculation. Values are the mean of 20
395 replicates, each represented by 1 plant. For each time of assessment the significance between
396 treatments was calculated according to Tukey's HSD test. Different letters indicate significant
397 differences at *P* level 0.05.

398

399 **4. Discussion**

400

401 In this paper, the activity of EAW towards Pch and Pmi was evaluated in controlled
402 conditions and in the nursery. EAW reduced conidial germination and EAW treatment during
403 hydration in the nursery caused a significant reduction of grafted cuttings infections. The
404 reduction of the wood infections was assessed at the end of the nursery process, on vines
405 ready to be planted in the vineyard in spring after winter cold storage.

406 Treatments with EAW did not reduce Pch or Pmi mycelial growth but were effective in
407 reducing conidial germination. Conidia of Pch seemed to be more sensitive than Pmi since
408 germination rate decreased with an increase of the exposition time to EAW. A strong EAW
409 activity towards spores of bacteria and fungi was reported by Abbasi and Lazarovitis (2006)
410 who showed that spores of *Streptomyces scabies*, *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *vesicatoria*,
411 and *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *lycopersici* were killed after an exposure of only 30 s to EAW.
412 Activity against conidial germination was also demonstrated on *Aspergillus flavus* (Xiong et
413 al., 2014). This ability to inhibit conidial germination can be particularly relevant in a GTDs
414 prevention strategy during the hydration stage in the nursery because when fungicides were
415 tested against Pmi and Pch (Groenewald et al., 2000; Jaspers, 2001; Gramaje et al., 2009),
416 their activity was mainly associated with the prevention of mycelial growth and not of conidia
417 germination, and so did not result in disinfection of the cutting. Those products were either
418 of doubtful efficacy [chinosol (8-hydroxyquinoline sulphate), Pertot et al., 2016], or gave

419 controversial or negative results (e.g thiophanate-methyl) on conidial germination inhibition
420 (Jaspers, 2001; Gramaje et al., 2009; Gramaje and Di Marco, 2015). To understand this lack
421 of efficacy it is important to understand that, on the contrary to EAW, fungicides applied in
422 hydration tanks, even if systemic, are not effectively absorbed and transported inside
423 cuttings as happens in vines in the field (Di Marco et al., 2009, 2012). Therefore, the use of
424 EAW can give a more successful disinfection compared to fungicides that probably lead to
425 a reduction of superficial fungal growth rather than a complete disinfection of the cutting
426 (Gramaje et al., 2009).

427 An important aspect that was clarified is that EAW is active even if it changes once
428 absorbed by the plant. The EAW quickly changes its physical-chemical characteristics and
429 the liquid - that we named weakened EAW (wEAW) - extracted from rootstocks immersed
430 up to 12 hours in EAW, showed a decrease of ORP (625-650 mV, about the 50% of the
431 EAW values) and a small increase of pH (3-3.5). The wEAW, despite the changed
432 characteristics due to the obvious presence of the sap extracted with the EAW water, still
433 caused a significant reduction of conidial germination of both fungal pathogens. Other
434 authors associated the activity of EAW against bacteria with ORP values exceeding 750
435 mV, with a concomitant action of protein degradation (Kim et al., 2000; Park et al. 2004);
436 while others demonstrated that ORP values close to 650 mV killed bacteria in a few seconds
437 (Cloete et al., 2009). The changes in pH can affect EAW activity, influencing the relative
438 fraction of chlorine in solution and increasing the formation of hypochlorous acid (Park et al.,
439 2004; Guentzel et al., 2006). Thus, Len et al. (2000) observed a maximum concentration of
440 HOCl at around pH 4, a value close to the ones assessed in wEAW. Therefore, it is possible
441 that the activity of wEAW assessed in the present study on inoculated vines could be also
442 associated with the high concentration of active chlorine in the solution.

443 The action of EAW is very rapid. Our data demonstrated that a few seconds of
444 exposure to EAW are enough to give a significant reduction in conidial germination.

445 Furthermore, a significant reduction was also achieved by contact with the liquid (wEAW)
446 extracted from the cuttings after hours of immersion. Therefore, the activity of EAW against
447 conidial germination of Pch and Pmi obtained by drenches or dips of infected propagation
448 material appears to have promising applications in the nursery process, providing care is
449 taken to avoid side effects such as corrosion of equipment or possible phytotoxicity.

450 No phytotoxic effect was recorded after exposure to EAW for the times tested in this
451 study. However, in preliminary trials prolonged immersion of cuttings in EAW (24 hours)
452 caused a slight discolouration of the wood surface (Di Marco and Osti, 2009). The
453 discolouration could be related with the association between chlorine content and time of
454 exposure (Izumi, 1999). Among the three different rootstock-scion combinations tested in
455 the present study, only K5BB showed a reduction of the percentage of vegetating and
456 certifiable cuttings when plants were hydrated for 12 hours in EAW. However, no effect was
457 observed at 7 hours of immersion, after which time the absorption of water was not
458 significantly different from that observed at 12 and 24 hours, confirming the adequate
459 hydration of the rootstock cuttings tested in this study.

460 The three-year experiments carried out in the nursery on cuttings inoculated with Pch
461 and hydrated in EAW showed a remarkable reduction of the infection level in the treated
462 plants. The reduction of the number of fragments colonized by Pch in EAW treated plants
463 decreased during the growth season, as also shown by Guentzel et al. (2006) but this
464 reduction remained statistically significant up to the end of the growth season when the
465 cuttings were uprooted. The long lasting effect found in this study could be an important
466 feature of EAW, also considering the different occasions of infection occurring during the
467 propagation process after hydration (Gramaje et al., 2009). It is possible that the loss of
468 chlorine due to volatilization, as shown by Guentzel et al. (2008) in long-term use, is lower
469 inside woody tissues thus ensuring a more persistent activity.

470 The EAW treatment reduced the internal colonization of the inoculated cuttings.
471 Colonization rate after artificial infection was higher at the base of the cutting, where the
472 spore suspension was absorbed, and decreased with increasing distance from the site of
473 inoculation. With a few exceptions, for each rootstock-scion combination, the level of activity
474 was consistent and comparable at all the tested distances from the site of inoculation (5–20
475 cm from the basal end). Most likely EAW, in addition to an external disinfection, can easily
476 reach all the internal part of the cuttings during hydration, thus providing uniform efficacy
477 along the entire length of the cutting on the conidia absorbed during artificial infection.

478 The activity of EAW towards Pch and Pmi is probably a result of the combination of
479 different mechanisms and modes of action due to the chlorine, low pH, high ORP, maybe
480 also involving the production of hydroxyl radical species, as suggested by Mokudai et al.
481 (2012). The main points of this study are the activity on conidial germination on important
482 GTDs pathogens and a long-term efficacy against germinating conidia in treated cuttings.
483 This of course does not prevent re-infection of the cuttings after the hydration.

484 Further studies on the combination of EAW with fungicides that are highly effective in
485 reducing mycelial growth, such as prochloraz, flusilazole, tebuconazole (Groenewald et al.,
486 2000; Jaspers 2001; Gramaje et al., 2009) or the possible combination with *Trichoderma*
487 applications during callusing and/or in the nursery field are required to evaluate the possible
488 synergistic effect of EAW with fungicides or biological control agents. In conclusion, EAW is
489 an environmentally friendly agent for the reduction of Pch and Pmi pathogens infections in
490 the nursery. This study was mainly directed to Pch, one of the most important grapevine
491 trunk disease pathogen, but it suggests new opportunities for the reduction of the general
492 level of contamination of vines in the nursery propagation process.

493

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498

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